

The poetic and linguistic structure of a *kunaung*: The story of Saripanta

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Kerinci, located in western Jambi Province, Sumatra, is home to the Kerinci language, a group of highly divergent Malay varieties. Like many other places in Indonesia, Kerinci's rich oral tradition is dying off. One genre of oral text in the area is the *kunaung*, a story which is sung by its reciter. This paper presents a brief summary of the Saripanta story, a *kunaung* from the village of Tanjung Pauh Mudik. In this paper, we describe the characteristics of its poetic and linguistic structure.

1. Introduction¹

Kerinci is a mountainous region in western Jambi Province, Sumatra. This region is home to the Kerinci language, which is a group of highly divergent Malay varieties. The traditional villages in Kerinci have a rich oral tradition that is quickly disappearing. A limited number of published volumes contain collections of traditional Kerinci oral literature. The largest of these are Zakaria (1981) *Kunaung: Kumpulan Cerita Rakyat Kerinci*, Udin, Esten, Semi, Busri, and Karim (1985) *Struktur Satra Lisan Kerinci*, and Esten & Usman's (1993) book which shares the same title. In addition, Kahar (1980), a general collection of folk tales from Jambi Province, contains some texts from Kerinci. Van Reijn (2001) contains a folktale from the village of Kumun in Kerinci.

Previous studies have classified oral texts in Kerinci by genre. Karimi (1968) (as cited by Udin *et al* (1985) for example, uses the terms *dongeng* (legends, myths, fables), *cerita penggeli hati* (comedy), *cerita pelibur lara* (lit. 'stories that console'), and *cerita perumpamaan* (allegory), *cerita pelengah* (lit. 'stories to pass time') and *kunaung*. The term *kunaung* (a cognate of the Malay *konon* 'once upon a time, purportedly'), is an original Kerinci term adopted by Zakaria (1981), and refers to a story sung (at least in part) by a *tukang kunaung* (the reciter of the *kunaung*). According to Karimi (1968), the *kunaung* is characteristically long, taking as long as seven nights to perform.

This paper takes a closer look at the elements of the *kunaung* genre. We examine *Saripanta*, a *kunaung* recorded and transcribed by Heri Mudra during fieldwork in Tanjung Pauh Mudik (Kerinci) in 2007-2008. Original recordings from our fieldwork are publically available from the TLA in Nijmegen (McKinnon, et. al 2016). We provide a brief summary of *Saripanta*, and examine its poetic and linguistic structure.

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2. Geography and linguistic situation in Kerinci

The Kerinci Regency is situated in western Jambi Province and is home to the Kerinci people, an ethnic group which speaks highly divergent Malay varieties collectively referred to as 'Kerinci'. This regency is situated in the Sumatran Barisan mountain range. The vast majority of Kerinci speakers reside in the expansive valley extending from Lake Kerinci in the south to the foothills of Mount Kerinci in the north. This valley is home to dozens of small traditional villages, which are separated by rice fields. In addition to traditional villages, there are also settlements of transmigrant Javanese, primarily in the north of the valley near the town of Kayu Aro. Significant populations of Minangkabau, Chinese, Batak, Javanese and other ethnicities reside in Sungai Penuh, the administrative center of the region.

There are roughly 260,000 speakers of Kerinci (www.ethnologue.com). This estimate needs some qualification: Firstly, while there is little question that those who identify as ethnic Kerinci also overwhelmingly identify themselves as speakers of Kerinci, it is unclear that linguistic criteria exist which would justify grouping Kerinci as a variety distinct from related languages spoken in other regions of western Jambi Province. Secondly, Kerinci is a hotspot of linguistic diversity. As Usman (1988) points out, dozens of distinct village dialects exist. The grammatical differences between varieties are often quite substantial, as a comparison of the few varieties which have been described to date makes apparent. The issue of Kerinci's status as a distinct linguistic group notwithstanding, one may legitimately question whether traditional Kerinci varieties constitute a single language or several distinct languages. Thirdly, as noted by Ernanda (2011), some regions of Kerinci have undergone dramatic language shift in recent years. One observable effect of language contact, especially in areas such as Sungai Penuh and Pondok Tinggi (where Minangkabau has overtaken Kerinci in many contexts) is the attrition of grammatical features characteristic of traditional Kerinci varieties, and the adoption of grammatical features characteristic of higher-prestige varieties of Malay/Indonesian. Mckinnon (2011) observes that many Kerinci speakers employ a Kerinci 'koine', a register which employs a mixture of general Malay/Indonesian features with lexical and phonological features which are iconic of Kerinci. Thus, as is the case in other regions in Indonesia, the complex sociolinguistic landscape in Kerinci makes it difficult to meaningfully estimate the number of native Kerinci speakers.

A few studies have focused on Kerinci grammar. Some major works in this area include Steinhauer & Usman (1978), Prentice & Usman (1978), Syahwin et al. (1981), Usman (1988), and Mckinnon (2011). Although these works show substantial differences between Kerinci varieties, they focus primarily on the varieties spoken in villages located in the immediate vicinity of Sungai Penuh. Little research has been conducted on varieties spoken in other regions of Kerinci.

Research on oral literature in Kerinci, much like research on Kerinci varieties, is limited in scope. From the accounts of elders, story and song played a prominent role in the past as a form of entertainment, a way of conferring local wisdom as well as maintaining customary law (*adat*).

3. Saripanta: A traditional *kunaung*

Saripanta is a traditional *Kunaung* from the village of Tanjung Pauh Mudik, Kerinci.² A written version of the story first appeared in Udin et al. with the title *Si Jaru Panta*. As we shall discuss below, the story recounts the journey of a young man, *Saripanta* (alternatively *Jarupanta*) who travels abroad to learn how to recite the Qur'an. *Saripanta* is a reappearing character in folktales throughout the Kerinci region, for instance in the story *Sijaro Panta*, a tale from Kumun, a neighboring village of Tanjung Pauh Mudik (Van Reijn, 2001). Indeed, as Van Reijn mentions (based on Voorhees) protagonists by the same name *Juara Pantang* (Malay, *lit.* 'champion of abstinence') appear in folktales throughout South Sumatra.³

The version of this story we discuss in this paper was collected in 2008 by Heri Mudra, a native of Tanjung Pauh Mudik. The elderly woman from whom the story was collected, is a relative of Heri Mudra's and, at the time of its recording, was one of four people remaining people in Tanjung Pauh still able to recite *Saripanta*. This version of the story has the same basic plot and main characters as the text collected by Udin *et al*; however, there are substantial differences with respect to the actual recited verses.

In what follows, we present a summary of *Saripanta* with examples taken from the transcription. The text is largely recited through song and consists of a limited number of frequently repeated melodies. In the section following our summary, we discuss the linguistic and poetic characteristics of *Saripanta*. On this basis, we draw some general conclusions about the *kunaung* genre.

Plot summary:

Saripanta is the story of a young man (alternately referred to as *Saripanta* and *Jarupanta*) who sets off on a journey to learn religion. On his journey, he is betrayed by his friend *Bujang Si Nganyang* (from the Malay *ganyang* 'eliminate, destroy'), who develops a scheme to trick *Ganduriyah* (*Saripanta*'s cousin and future wife) into marrying him.

The initial lines of the story introduce *Saripanta* as an individual of unique upbringing, who as a child abstained from drinking milk, and as an adult abstained from eating rice and the 'taking' of widows.

(1)

gi ni? bupanta jusāo.

When *Saripanta* was a child, he didn't drink breast milk.

la gdi bupanta nasāe
buji bupanta nambē? jandu,

After he had grown up, he didn't eat rice.
As a bachelor he abstained from taking a widow,

jandu si malāo bupanta jugu.

the timid widow abstained as well.

The lines which follow after the opening recount a dialogue between *Saripanta* and his closest friend *Bujang Si Nganyang*. The two lament how they have wasted their days chopping and hauling wood, while other their age have learned how to recite the Qur'an.

(2)

² The term for *kunaung* in the Tanjung Pauh Mudik dialect of Kerinci is *kunin*.

³ Date for Voorhees is not available.

‘in ^ə eh lah karj ⁱ w kito.’	‘This is our only work.’
‘in ^ə eh lah gaw ⁱ y kito.’	‘This is our only activity.’
‘ab ^l eh ara ^e di ⁿ ən ara ^e .’	‘Day after day are gone.’
‘abo ^e eh ara ^e di ⁿ ən ara ^e .’	‘Day after day are gone.’

The two men resolve to consult their families about their plan to go abroad to learn religion. Saripanta returns home to see his aunt, a widow who raised him. He tells her of his plan to go abroad for seven years to learn to recite the Qur’an. Saripanta’s aunt tells Saripanta that he is too young to make a journey abroad, and pleads with him not to leave her and his female cousin (Ganduriyah) alone in the village.

(3)	
‘ka ^o muranta ridi? lamo.’	‘I won’t go away for long.’
‘ka ^o muranta sibnti ralah.’	‘I’ll go away for just a while.’
‘ka l ^l η h ^ə tujuh taha ⁿ bari ^w n ^ə h pulo ka ^o bal ^l e?’	‘I will return within just seven years.’

Realizing that she cannot convince Saripanta otherwise, Saripanta’s aunt agrees to let him study religion abroad for seven years. A traditional feast is prepared and prayers are recited to bid the two men farewell, and to ensure their safe return. Saripanta’s aunt weeps while preparing Saripanta’s feast.

(4)	
‘la bugawi sam ^ə eh muna ⁿ æh.’	‘While I work, I cry.’
‘la muna ⁿ æh taki ^ç əo?-ki ^ç əo?’	‘I cry and sob.’
‘la muna ⁿ æh tasdi ^w -sdi ^w .’	‘I cry and sob.’

The morning after Saripanta’s farewell feast, a prayer is said, and Saripanta prepares to leave. Ganduriyah, his cousin and prospective wife, prepares clothes for Saripanta. Ganduriyah and Saripanta then set off to the seaside, followed by Saripanta’s aunt. When they arrive at the shore, they are told that the ship Saripanta wishes to take has already departed.

What happens next speaks to Ganduriyah’s unusual beauty. Spotting the ship on the sea, Ganduriyah waves her hands. The crew of the ship spots Ganduriyah waving from the shore, and enchanted by her looks, they return to land as quickly as they can.

(5)	
‘no mu ⁿ abit kito.’	‘She is waving at us.’
‘an ^ə o? r ^w əng mano pulo rit ^ə oh?’	‘Whose daughter is that?’
‘il ^l ? buk ^ə n kupala.’	‘Her beauty is extraordinary.’
‘il ^l ? buk ^ə n rulah.’	‘Her beauty is genuine.’
‘dari ^y ja ^ə oh nampa? ju ^g u.’	‘From afar it can be seen.’
la bubal ^l e? kpa ku t ^p æ.	The ship turned back toward the shore.
kpa buyali tilali ^w lkeh.	The ship sailed along so fast.
kpa buyali tilali ^w knča.	The ship sailed along so quickly.
pula ^o nampa, pula ^o puta ^o h.	Islands spread out far, islands divided.
tanj ^l nampa, tanj ^l puta ^o h.	Capes spread out far, capes divided.
no nd ^ə o? ηus ^ə e ganduriyah.	They wanted to reach Ganduriyah.
ma la knč ^ə η kpa ku t ^p iy, d ^e ??	They came back to shore so quickly.
n ^ə nd ^ə o? l ^ə eh ganduriyah.	They wanted to look at Ganduriyah.
n ^ə nd ^ə o? l ^ə eh liwa? n ^ə l ^y əo?, d ^e ??	They wanted to see how beautiful she was.
gi jah ^ə oh nampa? gu n ^ə l ^y l?	

From afar she looked so beautiful.

Arriving at the shore, the passengers disembark, hoping to catch a closer glimpse of Ganduriyah, and to ask her why she had waved at them. Taking advantage of the good will of the ship's crew, Ganduriyah asks whether there is room aboard the already full ship for Saripanta and his friend Bujang Si Nganyang.

- (6)
- | | |
|---|--|
| po ji katəo ganduriyah | Oh, the thing that Ganduriyah said was |
| 'lah yo kayo ne mama? eh, | 'Oh Sir, oh Uncle, ⁴ |
| mukəo ka ηabit kpən kayo, kətuwo ndəo? | The reason I waved at your ship, my |
| pglə ndəo? numpəη kpən kayo kalu | brother. |
| buləh.' | He would like to come aboard, if he may.' |
| 'kalu jiw? buləh məo?, juyadlə,' | 'If he cannot, then no need, he will not.' |
| ji katəo ganduriyah eh la ku padu tukəη | So said Ganduriyah to the ship's crew. |
| kpa. | |

The passengers agree to let the two aboard, and try unsuccessfully to convince Ganduriyah to board as well. As Saripanta departs to sea, his aunt and Ganduriyah begin to sob uncontrollably and pound at their chests.

- (7)
- | | |
|------------------------------------|---------------------------------------|
| sdiη niyən rasəo purase. | How sad was the feeling. |
| sdiη niyən rasəo atə. | How sad her heart felt. |
| ganduriyah munəηəh mungmpəη diriη. | Ganduriyah cried, pounding her chest. |
| tiransəo muηmpəη diriη. | Saripanta's aunt pounded her chest. |

Looking back from the ship, Saripanta wishes to return to his aunt and cousin, but cannot. Once the ship is far from shore, Ganduriyah asks her mother, Saripanta's aunt, to return home to the village.

- (8)
- | | |
|--|---|
| 'maaē la balə? kito, ndə.' | 'Let us go home, mother.' |
| 'kpən kətuwo ralah jaəoh.' | 'Older brother's ship is already far away.' |
| 'kpən kətuwo rlah jaəoh.' | 'Older brother's ship is already far away.' |
| 'idi? du nampa? laglə,' ji katəo ganduriyah. | 'It cannot be seen anymore,' Ganduriyah said. |
| no nəηəh takicəo?-kicəo?. | She cried and sobbed. |
| no nəηəh tasdiw sdiw. | She cried and wept. |
| tiransəo nangaəh jugu. | Her mother cried as well. |
| laliw balə? ranəo? r ^w əη itəoh | And so, she headed back home. |
| ndəe nə balə? jugu. | Her mother returned as well. |
| bujali saməh munəηəh muηəpiyη rayəe? | As they walked they cried and wiped away |
| matəo. | tears. |
| no sdiη bukən kupala. | Her sadness was extraordinary. |
| no sdiη bukən rulah eh. | Her sadness was genuine. |

After three days at sea, Saripanta and Bujang Si Nganyang arrive at their destination. The two, finding themselves disoriented in a foreign land, consider where they should go to learn to recite the Qur'an.

⁴ The term *mama?* (*lit.* 'uncle') is a polite term of address for older men.

(9)

apo ʒi katə̃ buʒaŋ si ŋanyaŋ la ku paɖiw
 ʒarupanta ‘lah yo kito ʒarupanta, manin ʒi
 kito inəeh?’
 ‘mano la tɪpɾə̃? ura ŋajlə̃?’ a ʒi katə̃
 buʒaŋ si ŋanyaŋ.

What Bujang Si Nganyang said to
 Saripanta was ‘Well Saripanta, what are
 we going to do now?’
 ‘In what place do people study religion?’
 Bujang Si Nganyang asked.

The two encounter an older man who takes them to a large mosque where others are studying recitation of the Qur’an. There, they meet the lead cleric at the mosque, who agrees to let them study along with the others. Soon after Saripanta and Bujang Si Nganyang begin their studies, it becomes apparent that Bujang Si Nganyang is not smart enough to follow the lessons given by the cleric.

(10)

diŋən muŋleuw ʒarupanta, ɲo ŋajlə̃ aɭŋ
 sura.
 diŋən muŋliw buʒəŋ si ŋaŋəŋ, la lamo ɲo
 nəh ŋajlə̃, ridi? ʒugu adu taɦo.

As for Saripanta, he had recited the Qur’an
 in the mosque.

And as for Bujang Si Nganyang, for a long
 time he had been learning, but he
 nevertheless knew nothing.

diŋən muŋliw ʒarupanta, ɭ dikato ɲo lah
 pande, ɭ dikato, ɲo lah taɦo.
 ruo ɲo ura ridak ratiy.

As for Saripanta, he knew and understood
 things before they were said.

He had a bright heart.

diŋən muŋliw buʒəŋ si ŋaŋəŋ, lah puweh
 gurɪw munra, lah puweh gurɪw mungajɪ.

As for Bujang Si Nganyang, the cleric was
 tired of explaining things to him and tired
 of teaching him

ridi? ʒugu adu taɦo.
 ruo nyo ura mateuy rataé.

Unfortunately, he didn’t know anything.
 It seems Bujang Si Nganyang had a dark
 heart.

Frustrated by his failure, Bujang Si Nganyang decides to leave his studies and become a beggar, despite Saripanta’s repeated attempts to convince him to stay at the mosque. After leaving his studies, Bujang Si Nganyang spends his days begging at the harbor. Meanwhile, Saripanta excels under the instruction of the cleric. The cleric makes Saripanta his assistant.

One day a ship crew arrives at the harbour carrying a letter from Ganduriyah. A sailor, wishing to deliver the letter to Saripanta, asks Bujang Si Nganyang where Saripanta has gone to study the Qur’an. Bujang Si Nganyang tells the sailor that he and Saripanta live together and offers to deliver the letter to Saripanta himself. Rather than delivering the letter to Saripanta, however, Bujang Si Nganyang opens the letter himself.

(11)

apo ʒi katə̃ baču sura?
 ɲo manuwe? ʒarupanta
 ‘pilu balə̃? kayo, kutuwo?’ ʒi katə̃
 ganduriyah.

What is the thing that he read in the letter?
 She asked Saripanta:
 ‘When will you come back, brother?’
 Ganduriyah asked.

Bujang Si Nganyang destroys the letter and returns to the place where he and Saripanta stay. That same evening Saripanta dreams that he is eating together with his aunt and Ganduriyah. Saripanta awakes from the dream, and wakes up Bujang Si Nganyang to tell him what he has dreamt.

- (12)
 ‘akaō mimp̄l̄e maka sirm̄pa? diṅən
 tiransāō.’ ‘I dreamt that I was eating together with
 my aunt.’
 ‘maka sidaō diṅən adiy?.’ ‘I ate from the same leaf as Ganduriyah.’

Saripanta interprets his own dream as a sign that Ganduriyah or his aunt has sent him a letter. Saripanta tells Bujang Si Nganyang to ask the crew of the ship if they had been entrusted with a letter from his family. The next day, and in the days that would follow, Bujang Si Nganyang tells Saripanta that no letter has arrived from his aunt or Ganduriyah. Bujang Si Nganyang also assures Saripanta that his dream is meaningless. Eventually, Saripanta decides to compose his own letter to Ganduriyah.

- (13)
 diṅən muṅliw ṅarupanta, po ṅi katō surət As for Saripanta, what was in his letter?
 ṅo pulo.
 ‘lah yo kayo tiransāō, lah yo m̄p̄l̄ n̄h ‘Oh my aunt and sister,
 adiy?,
 la dki? rndō? bal̄e? akaō n̄h, rad̄l̄e? soon I shall return, oh my sister.’
 l̄eh.’
 ‘idi? lamo ḡiy k̄o muranta.’ ‘I shall not stay abroad much longer.’
 ‘akaō la dapi? ṅadiy ḡuriw.’ ‘I have managed to become a teacher.’
 ‘akaō muṅaji ranō? sikula,’ ṅi katō ‘I teach students,’ said in his letter.
 ṅarupanta l̄ suhət tah.
 ‘k̄o la dapi? ṅadi ḡuriw,’ ṅi ṅə to, d̄e?? ‘I have managed to become a teacher,’ he
 said.

Not knowing his friend’s intention to read and destroy his letter, Saripanta entrusts the letter with Bujang Si Nganyang, who has offered to deliver it to the ship crew at the harbor.

- (14)
 he diṅən muṅliw ṅarupanta, sna lah pulo Hey, as for Saripanta, his heart was now
 hatiy ṅo tadiyh. filled with joy.
 sudih dikirih sura? pulo. The letter had been sent.
 psa sudih tikiraṅ pulo. The message had been conveyed.
 sna tiy ṅarupanta, d̄e?? Saripanta was delighted.

Several weeks pass with no reply, and Saripanta begins to suspect that his aunt has become angry with him. He decides to compose another letter to his aunt, which he once again entrusts to Bujang Si Nganyang. Receiving no response to his second letter, Saripanta becomes convinced that his aunt is angry with him. Bujang Si Nganyang offers to travel home to explain all that has happened while the two were abroad. Saripanta agrees, but when Saripanta asks to join him, Bujang Si Nganyang insists that Saripanta stay behind. Saripanta then prepares gifts for Bujang Si Nganyang to bring back to Ganduriyah.

- (15)
 dibliy pulo ṅo n̄h tra? adu sirle. He bought her one sarong.
 kaē adu sirle. There was also one length of cloth.
 baṅō adu sirle. and also one dress.
 tirunt̄? ndō? adiy?. especially for his sister.

When Bujang Si Nganyang comes into the harbor, news of his arrival reaches Ganduriyah, who assumes that Saripanta has returned with him. Ganduriyah rushes home to tell her mother to prepare for Saripanta's return. After some time, Ganduriyah's servant, Puti Sembahyang Air Ameh, arrives at the house and tells Ganduriyah and her mother that Bujang Si Nganyang has arrived alone.

(16)

<p>apo ji katəo putiy simiya rayəe? ameh ku padiw ganduriyah 'piyo iko muṅmba tika?' 'piyo iko muṅajḷḷə lapə?'' 'ketuwo mṛḷ ridi? baləe?, buṅṅ si nganṅə baləe? sura,' ji katəo budiw? gadləh ganduriyah.</p>	<p>The thing that Puteuy Simiya Rayeéq Améh said to Ganduriyah is: 'why have you spread out a rug?' 'Why do you set out a mat?' 'Your brother has not come back, Bujang Si Nganyang came back alone,' said Ganduriyah's female servant.</p>
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Ganduriyah and her mother go to see Bujang Si Nganyang, to ask him why Saripanta has not yet returned. Bujang Si Nganyang lies to Ganduriyah and her mother, recounting how Saripanta had failed his studies and had set out on his own to make a living catching fish in a river contaminated with diseases.

(17)

<p>'lah lamo kamae busre.' 'idi? adu situmpa? lagləe.' 'idi? adu sirmpa? lagləe.' 'no ḡajlə ndi? dapi?.' 'adu lah bitu jaəoh sikaləe.' 'adu lah bitu lamo siduləo.' no tipasa ka rulu ayə?, muṅujḷḷḷə tanḡḷ sibuwih. 'muṅinḡə? ragu sibuwih.' 'no nanḡəo? udi siganti sarəe.' 'no nanḡəo? siluwa sačupa? sarəe.' 'ura dusḷḷə ritəoh bupanta mininḡ ayə? sungəe ritəoh he.'</p>	<p>'We have been separated for a long time' 'We do not live in the same place anymore' 'We are no longer together.' 'He did not learn how to recite the Qur'an.' 'There was once news from afar,' 'There was news from long ago.' He was forced to go to the headwaters of a river, he carried a net to catch fish' He brought a bamboo basket.' 'He caught shrimp, a quart a day.' 'He caught <i>siluang</i> fish, a scoop a day.' 'Hey, the villagers there avoided drinking the water from that river.'</p>
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Ganduriyah refuses to believe the bad news which Bujang Si Nganyang has brought, and insists that she and her mother go home. Her mother refuses to return home, since she, like the others in the village is enchanted by Bujang Si Nganyang, who she believes has become a learned man.

Bujang Si Nganyang urges Ganduriyah and her mother to mother to forget about Saripanta, since he may never return. He also asks permission to visit Ganduriyah's house with gifts in a few days time.

(18)

<p>'adu ndəo? ka bagləh ḡusəe radləe? eh' ḡambəe? kahe radu sirle. magləh tra? radu sirle. magləh bajəo radu sirle. 't'əoh lah radu.' 't'əoh lah radu a mahəo,' jiy.</p>	<p>'I am going to give something for my sister', he took out the piece of cloth. He gave her the sarong. He gave her the dress. 'I only have these.'</p>
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‘I brought only these,’ he said.

When Bujang Si Nganyang later arrives with gifts at the home of Ganduriyah and her mother, Ganduriyah refuses to leave her bedroom, knowing that Bujang Si Nganyang intends to propose marriage to her. After a long wait, Bujang Si Nganyang decides to ask Ganduriyah’s mother for her hand in marriage rather than propose to her directly. Convinced that Saripanta will never return home, Ganduriyah’s mother accepts Bujang Si Nganyang’s proposal.

(19)

he la lamo dudəo? di rumih,
po ji katəo bujəŋ si ŋəŋəŋ
‘lah yo kayo tiransəo,
akəo inəeh ndəo? butuwe? padu kayo.’
‘he mbəh kayo muniməo akəo?’
‘akəo ndəo? baləe? ku ruməoh kayo.’
la, la nasa?

‘a lah yo,’ katəo tiransəo.
‘lamba? ko tibu, lamba? lah gmpu m^wah la
rubəoh.’

‘lamba? ko ngato, kamae la rmbəh.’

‘After sitting in the house for a long time,
what Bujang Si Nganyang said was this:
‘Oh Auntie, I want to ask you something.’

‘Hey, would you to accept me?’
‘I want to marry Ganduriyah (lit. return to
your house).’

He started to build a wall.⁵

‘Oh yes’ Saripanta’s aunt said.

‘Long before you came, before any
earthquake hit, the house had already
collapsed.’

‘Before you spoke of it, we already wanted
it.’

Having overheard the conversation between Bujang Si Nganyang and her mother, Ganduriyah breaks down in tears. Later, she tells her mother that she refuses to marry Bujang Si Nganyang. Ganduriyah’s mother responds by threatening to kill herself if the two do not marry.

(20)

he diŋən muŋliw ganduriyah,
‘lah yo kayo neh nde, ka d^yi? randəo?
kawan, eh.’
‘la katuwəo baləe?, la ka ndəo? kawan,’

ji katəo ganduriyah ku padiw ndəe no
pulo.

no nangaeh tikiçəo?-kiçəo?

no nangaeh tasdiw-sdiw.

no tina katuwəo sura.

po ji katəo ndəo no pulo,

‘lah yo rana? kaə sura, turak ka bae katəo
akəo!’

‘kalu ndi? mɾə munurik katəo akəo, kaə
ndəo? munəoh dirəe, ganduriyah.’

‘biyi lah kaə matae, ganduriyah.’

‘tuŋgəo di mɾə ruməoh gdi!’

Hey, Ganduriyah complained:

‘Oh Mother, I do not want to get married.’

‘Until Saripanta returns, I do not want to
marry,’

said Ganduriyah said to her mother.

She cried and sobbed.

She cried and wept.

She missed her only brother.

What is the thing her mother then said:

‘Oh my only child, just follow what I say!’

‘If you do not want to follow what I say, I
shall kill myself, Ganduriyah.’

‘Just let me die, Ganduriyah.’

‘You go on and live in a big house!’

⁵ This is a metaphor for engagement.

‘tun̄gāo di m̄pΛ hart̄o b̄ani?!’
ji nd̄æ n̄ə, d̄e??

‘You just go on living with abundant
wealth!’ said her mother.

In a final effort to save herself from becoming Bujang Si Nganyang’s wife, Ganduriyah rushes to the seaside and entrusts one more letter for Saripanta to the crew of the ship. Knowing that the ship crew might not deliver the letter out of jealousy, much as Bujang Si Nganyang had, Ganduriyah leads the crew to believe that Saripanta is actually her younger sibling, and that he must return because their mother has fallen ill. Upon receiving this letter, Saripanta sets off immediately for home, though his students beg him to stay.

(21)

he la mūnimba? pulo jarupanta,
‘he kyo r^wanj b̄ani?, m̄o? lah iko munah̄n
akāo!’
‘kāo lah lamo kāo di siniy.’
‘l̄ p̄ernah mūjir̄ə̄n̄ sura?.’
‘l̄ p̄ernah munim̄ō psa.’
‘in̄ə̄h la tibu psen,’ j̄iy.
‘m̄o? lah ko nah̄n kāo!’

Hey, Saripanta spoke,
‘Oh People, do not hold me back!’
‘I have been here for a long time.’
‘I have never sent a letter.’
‘I have never received a message.’
‘Now, a message has come,’ he said.
‘Do not hold me back!’

Saripanta returns home to find that the harbor is quiet. An old man he encounters tells him that all of the villagers have gone to attend the wedding of Ganduriyah and Bujang Si Nganyang. Hearing the sound of a gong, Saripanta knows that Ganduriyah has already been married off. The old man asks Saripanta why he has broken out in tears. Saripanta responds by telling the old man about his unusual upbringing, expounding on the meaning of his given name, *Jarupanta/Saripanta* (literally ‘champion/essence of abstinence’). At this point, Saripanta returns to the opening lines of the *kunaung*.

(22)

‘agi ni? bupanta nūsāo.’
‘la gdi bupanta nasāe.’
‘la buji bupanta ṅamb̄e? j̄andu.’

When I was a child, I did not drink milk.
When I grew up, I didn’t eat rice
As a bachelor I abstained from taking a
widow.

Saripanta weeps before the old man, since he has no place to call home. Bujang Si Nganyang, by custom, will stay with Saripanta’s aunt and Ganduriyah following the wedding. The old man takes pity on Saripanta and offers to adopt him and to find him a beautiful wife. The two set off for the old man’s home. On the way, they run into the wedding party and are forced to walk through the crowd. Seeing Saripanta, the crowd falls silent.

Noticing a change in the crowd, Ganduriyah’s servant, Puti Sembahyang Air Ameh peeks out of the house, spots Saripanta and informs Ganduriyah that Saripanta has returned from abroad. Ganduriyah takes off all her wedding jewelry and leaves the house to find Saripanta, although her mother begs her to stay. She follows Saripanta to the old man’s home. At first, Saripanta refuses to speak with Ganduriyah, since she is now Bujang Si Nganyang’s wife.

Saripanta’s aunt arrives at the house and tells Ganduriyah and Saripanta to return home. Ganduriyah lets down her hair and takes out a knife which she has hidden in her hair bun. Ganduriyah threatens to stab herself. The old man intercedes at this point and convinces them return to Ganduriyah’s mother’s house. When Ganduriyah, Saripanta,

his aunt (Ganduriyah's mother) and the old man arrive at the house, wedding food is prepared and eaten. When the meal is over, the four of them eat betel together.

Below Ganduriyah's mother's house a crowd gathers with Bujang Si Nganyang, who yells out to Saripanta, threatening to kill him since he has taken his new wife, Ganduriyah. After much provocation, Saripanta confronts Bujang Si Nganyang.

We note that, after this point in the story, the version of *Saripanta* collected by Heri Mudra differs from the older version of *Saripanta* in Udin *et al* (1985). The woman recorded in Heri Mudra's version was already quite elderly when the story was collected, and she unfortunately had forgotten many of the remaining verses of *Saripanta*. The text which appears in Udin *et al* tells of a number of extraordinary and magical events which culminate in an attempt to reverse Ganduriyah's marriage to Bujang Si Nganyang. We do not discuss these events in detail, since they were not recounted in the version we collected.

After Saripanta confronts Bujang Si Nganyang, he and Ganduriyah flee into the jungle. Later, the two arrive near a poisoned river, where Saripanta takes a drink of water and falls unconscious. Believing that Saripanta has died, Ganduriyah becomes desperate, leaves the poisoned river and sets off on her own. Reaching the shore, she meets a sultan and boards his ship. Meanwhile, Saripanta awakes from his deep sleep and realizes Ganduriyah is gone. Saripanta immediately suspects she has been kidnapped and sets off to find her.

Saripanta's journey involves numerous magical occurrences which eventually lead him back to Ganduriyah. At the end of the tale, Ganduriyah agrees to marry Saripanta, but under one condition, which is impossible by the rules of nature. The two plant bamboo shoots on opposing shores of a river. When the two bamboo shoots grow together to form one, Saripanta will be allowed to wed Ganduriyah.

4. General discussion of the poetic and linguistic structure of Saripanta

In the preceding section we provided a general summary of *Saripanta*, a *kunaung* from the traditional Kerinci village of Tanjung Pauh. In this section, we take a closer look at its linguistic properties. We present some notes on the linguistic features of *Saripanta* which stand out as unusual in the context of what is otherwise found in the naturalistic corpus of Tanjung Pauh (<https://corpus1.mpi.nl/ds/asv/?1>). Although we hesitate to claim that the properties we discuss in this section are exclusive to the genre of the *kunaung*, we think that these properties represent a solid basis for understanding how the *kunaung* differs from other types of text.

disyllabicity vs. monosyllabicity

Like other traditional Malay varieties (Malay varieties spoken in rural villages, as distinct from urban varieties based on a mixture of many different dialects and languages), lexical roots in Kerinci are prototypically disyllabic; however, in some Kerinci varieties, including Tanjung Pauh, monosyllabic truncated roots are very frequently encountered in naturalistic speech, as exemplified below.

(23) Truncation

$C_1V_1C_2V_2(C_3)$	$>$	$V_1C_2V_2(C_3)$	$>$	$C_2V_2(C_3)$	
maka		aka		ka	'eat'
hataē		ataē		tāē	'heart, liver'

in *Saripanta* than in other types of texts in the Tanjung Pauh corpus. The following are a few words that frequently appear with epenthetic *r* in the story.

(27) Common form	Form w/epenthetic <i>r</i>	Gloss
(a)d $\overline{\text{a}}\text{e}?$	rad $\overline{\text{a}}\text{e}?$	‘younger sibling’
lah	r(a)lah	PAST
il $\overline{\text{a}}?$	ril $\overline{\text{a}}?$	‘good, beautiful’
(s)idiw $\overline{?}/\overline{?}iw?$	ridi $\overline{?}$	NEG
(la)g $\overline{\text{a}}\text{e}$	rag $\overline{\text{a}}\text{e}$	‘again’

The following tables display the frequency of epenthetic *r*-initial forms in *Saripanta* versus other texts for four roots which undergo this process.

(28)

	Saripanta			Other naturalistic texts		
	r-epenthesis	Basic	truncated	r-epenthesis	basic	truncated
‘to be’ (A)	Radu	Adu	du	Radu	adu	du
Tokens	14	75	93	2	209	647
% of overall occurrences	7.7%	41.2%	51.1%	0.2%	24.4%	75.4%

	Saripanta			Other naturalistic texts		
	r-epenthesis	Basic	truncated	r-epenthesis	basic	truncated
‘child’ (O)	ran $\overline{\text{a}}\text{o}?$	an $\overline{\text{a}}\text{o}?$	n $\overline{\text{a}}\text{o}?$	ran $\overline{\text{a}}\text{o}?$	an $\overline{\text{a}}\text{o}?$	n $\overline{\text{a}}\text{o}?$
Tokens	19	18	22	26	81	287
% of overall occurrences	32.2%	30.5%	37.3%	6.6%	20.6%	72.8%

	Saripanta			Other naturalistic texts		
	r-epenthesis	Basic	truncated	r-epenthesis	basic	truncated
‘that’	rit $\overline{\text{a}}\text{o}h$	it $\overline{\text{a}}\text{o}h$	t $\overline{y}\overline{\text{a}}\text{o}h$	rit $\overline{\text{a}}\text{o}h$	it $\overline{\text{a}}\text{o}h$	t $\overline{y}\overline{\text{a}}\text{o}h$
Tokens	15	23	54	19	23	498
% of overall occurrences	16.0%	25%	58.7%	3.5%	4.3%	92.2%

	Saripanta			Other naturalistic texts		
	r-epenthesis	Basic	truncated	r-epenthesis	basic	truncated
1SG	rak $\overline{\text{a}}\text{o}$	ak $\overline{\text{a}}\text{o}$	k $\overline{\text{a}}\text{o}$	rak $\overline{\text{a}}\text{o}$	ak $\overline{\text{a}}\text{o}$	k $\overline{\text{a}}\text{o}$
Tokens	2	100	118	6	352	516
% of overall occurrences	.9%	45.5%	53.6%	.7%	40.3%	59%

As shown in the above tables, in *Saripanta* text, the epenthetic *r*-initial forms are more frequently found (i.e. 7.7%, 32.2%, 16%, and 0.9% ‘to be’, ‘child’, ‘that’, and ‘I’, respectively) than those in naturalistic texts (i.e. 0.2%, 6.6%, 3.5%, and 0.7%, respectively). The tables also show that the truncation to a monosyllable is much less frequent in *Saripanta* than in other naturalistic texts. The truncated forms of *adu* ‘to be’,

anə̌o? ‘child’, *itə̌oh* ‘that’, and *akə̌o* ‘1SG’ occur 51.1%, 37.3%, 58.7%, and 53.5% in Saripanta text, whereas these forms occur 75.4%, 72.8%, 92.2%, and 59%, respectively in other naturalistic texts.

R-insertion is likely to serve as a strategy to build word-forms which conform to the proto-typical word-shape mentioned in the previous subsection. *R*-insertion occurs both in vowel-initial disyllabic roots and roots in which the onset of penultimate syllables historically contained a consonant onset. However, it is unclear whether the underlying form of consonant-initial roots lacks a consonant, or whether the rule of r-epenthesis is fed by the deletion rule which results in truncation.

Relative clauses headed by diηən

The relative clause marker in Tanjung Pauh Kerinci is *ηən*. Synchronically, this marker is homophonous with the truncated form of the preposition *diηən* ‘with’. Speakers reject otherwise grammatical relative clauses in which the morpheme *ηən* is replaced with the form *diηən*. Interestingly, however, in *Saripanta*, there are numerous examples in which the morpheme *diηən* functions as a relative clause marker.

(29) *sapo pulo diηən balə̌e?*
 who.N again.N with.N return.A
 ‘who is it that has returned?’

(30) *ambə̌e? kahε diηən bu-namo*
 take.O cloth.A with.N BU.name.A
 ‘Take a cloth which has a well-know name (a well known brand).’

(31) *ridi? adu diηən balə̌e?*
 NEG exist.A with.N return.A
 ‘There was nobody who returned.’

These examples suggest that the functional distinction between the relative clause marker and preposition ‘with’ was not present in a more archaic form of the language.

Prevalence of object voice constructions

Much like Standard Malay/Indonesian (MacDonald and Dardjowidjojo, 1967 *inter alia*) and Traditional Jambi Malay (Cole, Hermon and Yanti, 2008; Yanti, 2010), transitive clauses in Tanjung Pauh Mudik Kerinci generally have one of three voice types: *active* (the verb is marked with an active voice prefix), *di-passive* (the verb is marked with the prefix *di-*, and object voice (the verb appears in its ‘bare’ form).⁶ The object voice construction is a passive-type construction in which the patient/theme is in the subject position, the agent is always adjacent to the verb and the verb used is in bare form (cf. Sneddon, 1996; Cole et al., 2006). This passive type is frequently referred to as object voice (MacDonald and Dardjowidjojo, 1967) or as the passive type-2 construction. The object voice construction is noticeably more frequent in *Saripanta* than in conversational speech. As already mentioned, in the object voice construction, the undergoer argument appears as the subject (and may undergo extraction), while the

⁶ Linguists have used various terms to discuss this construction, among them are ‘passive type-2’, ‘bare passive’ and ‘pasif semu.’

agent (which is a non-3rd person pronoun) appears immediately before the verb. While this construction is rarely attested in naturalistic texts of everyday speech, it occurs frequently in *Saripanta*. The following are examples of this structure.

(32) ‘*sapo ka tantɛʔ balæʔʔ*’
 who.A 1.SG wait.N return.A

‘Who will I await the return of?’

(33) ‘*sapo diŋen kɑ̄o rasahʔ*’
 who.A REL 1.SG raise.A

‘Who will I take care of?’

(34) ‘*sapo diŋən kɑ̄o surahʔ*’
 who.A REL 1.SG order.N

‘Who will I ask for help?’

Organization of verses

We observe that the structure of verses follows certain frequently repeated patterns throughout *Saripanta*. In general, couplets tend to consist of two or three lines, each of which contains roughly the same numbers of syllables and rhythmic pattern. Each line in typically consists of 7-9 syllables.

(35) a. *aya lah sudih bu-kukʌʔ*
 chicken.A PAST PERF BU-crow.A

‘Chickens have already sounded.’

b. *mure la sudih muŋiĉa*
 murai.A PAST PERF N.chirp.A

‘Murai birds have already chirped.’

Verses of this form generally follow one of two patterns. In many verses, the second line is identical to the first with the exception of one or two words. Those words which differ between lines are typically synonyms.

(36) a. ‘*inæh lah karjɪw kito.*’
 this.N just.N work.O 1.PL

‘This is our only work.’

b. ‘*inæh lah gawiy kito.*’
 this.N just.N work.O 1.PL

‘This is our only work.’

(37) a. *no naŋæh ta-kiĉəʔ-kiĉəʔ*
 3 ACT.cry.A TER-RED-sob.N

‘She cried with sobs.’

b. *no nangaeh ta-sdiw-sdiw.*
 3 ACT.cry.A TER-RED-sob.N

‘She cried with sobs.’

(38) a. ‘*subu lah pikæ badan akɑ̄o*’
 try.A just.N think.O body.O 1.SG

‘Please, think of me.’

- b. *'subu lah rinΛη badΛn akāo'*
 try.A just.N remember.O body.O 1.SG
 'Please remember me.'

In other examples, the second line of the verse differs in content, but exhibits the same clause structure as the first line.

- (39) a. *'ulāē? dani la tipanča'*
 rainbow.A PAST TER-appear.N
 'A rainbow rises up.'
- b. *'kumbΛ-kumbΛ lah titgi?'*
 RED-spout.A PAST TER-stand.A
 'Spouts have already appeared.'

To some extent, the final syllables of verses contain the same final word, syllable or rhyme.

- (40) a. *duliw yo kamāē situmpa?*
 before.N yes.A 1.PL one.place.A
 'We once were in the same place.'
- b. *'duliw yo kamāē sirmpa?'*
 before.N yes.A 1.PL together.N
 'We used to be together.'
- c. *'lah lamo kamāē bu-čre.'*
 PAST long.A 1.PL BU-separate.N
 'We separated a long time ago.'
- d. *'idi? adu bu-suwo agih.'*
 NEG exist BU-meet again
 'We (bujang si nganyang and saripanta) don't see each other anymore.'
- (41) a. *'idi? mbΛh di-čgih lagΛē.'*
 NEG.N want.N PASS-prevent.N again.A
 'You cannot be stopped anymore.'
- b. *'idi? mbΛh di-taha lagΛē.'*
 NEG.N want.N PASS-bear.A again.A
 'You cannot be held back anymore.'
- c. *diḡən muḡluh ḡarupanta jo ta kréh niyen ndāo? pḡΛē.*
 REL ACT.complaint.N Saripanta.N 3 that hard.A very.N want.N go.A
 'As for Saripanta, he really wanted to go.'

Topic stating contructions with maḡleuw(h)

The phrase *diḡən maḡleuw(h)*, which could be translated literally as 'with complaint', often appears at the beginning of verses. In addition to expressing actual complaint, this phrase in most cases simply functions to introduce or change the topic of the following line(s). In the examples below, *diḡən maḡliwh* is used to mark several sequential changes in topic.

- (42) diṅən muṅliwh ṅarupanta, ɲo ɲaj̄l̄e alɒŋ sura. As for Saripanta, he had recited the Qur'an in the mosque.
- diṅən muṅliwh buṅəŋ si ɲəɲəŋ, la lamo ɲo nəh As for Bujang Si Nganyang, for a long time he had been learning, but he nevertheless knew nothing.
- ɲaj̄l̄e, ridi? jugu adu tahaō. As for Saripanta, he knew and understood things before they were said. He had a bright heart.
- diṅən muṅliwh ṅarupanta, la dikato ɲo lah pande, la dikato, ɲo lah taao. As for Saripanta, he knew and understood things before they were said. He had a bright heart.
- rupo ɲo ura ridak ratiy. As for Bujang Si Nganyang, the cleric was tired of explaining things to him and tired of teaching him.
- diṅən muṅliwh buṅəŋ si ɲəɲəŋ, lah puweh gur̄iw munra, lah puweh gur̄iw mungaṅi.

'Reported speech' with *apo ṅi katəō*

The phrase *apo ṅi katəō* frequently occurs in contexts where the narrator reports the direct speech of a character. The phrase can be translated roughly as 'what X said was...'. This construction is much less frequent in other types of naturalistic text. The following examples illustrate this construction.

- (43) apo ṅi katəō tukəŋ kpa kupadiw ha dusɒŋ itəoh:
 what.N say.O agent.O ship.A to person.A village.O that.N
 'What the ship crew asked the villagers was:'

mano tɲpəe? ṅarupanta ɲaj̄l̄e dusiŋ inəeh?
 which.N place.O Saripanta.N ACT.read.O village.O this.N

'Where is the place where Saripanta recites the Qur'an in this village.'

5. General discussion and conclusion

Let us draw some general conclusions regarding the *kunaung* genre, based on the example of *Saripanta*. Udin et. al. (1985) has noted that only certain individuals—those capable of immersing themselves in the emotions of a storyline—are effective in telling a *kunaung*. The expressive demands of the *kunaung* along with its extraordinary length (which Udin et. al. note may be as long as seven nights) makes it impossible for the *tukan kunaung* to deliver the *kunaung* verbatim. The *tukan kunaung* must rely on clever impromptu innovations, while remaining faithful to the basic elements of the story (e.g. the plot, characters, theme, setting). A comparison of the two available versions of *Saripanta* illustrates just how much creative license is involved in the actual recitation. Although both versions of *Saripanta* were collected from the same village (within roughly a 20 year span), follow the same plot line, and adhere to similar poetic conventions, these texts nevertheless share very few identical verses. This is in line with previous studies which discuss oral formulaic language, such as Fox (2000), who explores oral formulaic language in Rote, eastern Indonesia.

We have also noted several linguistic features which distinguish *Saripanta* from other texts in our naturalistic corpus. For example, we demonstrated a strong stylistic preference for disyllabic consonant-initial forms in *Saripanta*, for instance words which

are frequently truncated tend to appear in their full, disyllabic form, or with an epenthesized *r*. There are a number of hypotheses which might explain the origins of this stylistic phenomenon. One hypothesis is that these forms are simply archaic, and have been preserved in limited, highly conventionalized genres, such as the *kunaung*. Hypothesis 2: acrolectal imitation. Hypothesis 3: the metrical structure of the *kunaung* itself demands these forms.

Abbreviations

List all the abbreviations used in your paper, including those in the Leipzig Glossing Rules list, here.

1	first person
3	third person
A	ablaut
ACT	active
BU	a prefix
N	neutral
NEG	negative marker
O	oblique
PAST	past
PFCT	perfective
PL	plural
RED	reduplication
REL	relativizer
SG	singular

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